

X-31A QUASI-TAILLESS EVALUATION

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Abstract -The X-31A is a single seat, single engine airplane designed to explore maneuverability at angles of attack up to 70 degrees. It is a delta wing and canard design which incorporates multi-axis thrust vectoring to augment conventional flight control surfaces.

The U.S. Joint Advanced Strike Technology (JAST) program tasked the X-31 International Test Organization (ITO) to obtain flight test data on the use of thrust vectoring for control augmentation of tailless airplanes. This was due to the JAST Program's requirement to investigate the feasibility of future strike aircraft designs with reduced, or no vertical tail. The X-31 flight control system software was modified to incorporate a quasi-tailless mode whereby the directional stability provided by the aircraft's vertical tail was incrementally reduced.

A flight test evaluation was conducted to evaluate the use of thrust vectoring to augment an aircraft that was made directionally unstable via the conventional flight control system. The evaluation was centered around high gain mission tasks including precision approach and air-to-ground attack maneuvers. The tasks were: 1) Fixed reticle capture of the Adaptable Target

Lighting Array System (ATLAS). This system consists of an array of ground fixed lights for air-to-ground target capture tasks. 2) Mission representative air-to-ground delivery profiles. 3) Nominal and offset approaches using the U.S. Navy's Fresnel precision approach glide path indication system. The fact that the airplane was not designed for the air-to-ground or for the carrier based role made the task development challenging.

This paper discusses the flight test approach, buildup and conduct, test results and design considerations for future tailless aircraft.

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NOMENCLATURE

CIC	Close In Combat
AOA	Angle of Attack
CR	Cruise (landing gear up, high lift deselected)
FCC	Flight Control Computer
fpm	feet per minute
fps	feet per second
ITO	International Test Organization
JAST	Joint Affordable Strike Technology
LEF	Leading Edge Flap
NAWC-AD	Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division, Patuxent River, MD 20670
PA	Power Approach (landing gear down, high lift selected)
SAM	Surface to Air Missile
TEF	Trailing Edge Flap
TVV	Thrust Vectoring Vane(s)
TV	Thrust Vectoring

1. INTRODUCTION

The X-31 Program was begun in 1985 in response to theories put forth by the former Dr. Herbst and Mr. Richard Haiplik. The intent of the program was to investigate the tactical utility of thrust vectoring and post stall maneuvering in the Close In Combat arena. The X-31 ITO flew the CIC research from November of 1993 to November of 1994, for a total of 82 flights.

The formal results from the CIC testing are forthcoming, but may be summarized as follows:

1. Post stall maneuvering offers:
 - a. A significant tactical advantage from a position of conventional parity.
 - b. Increased survivability from a position of conventional performance deficit.
 - c. Shorter engagement times.

- d. Defensive survivability is greatly increased.

- e. Requires judicious use.

2. The next generation of fighter - attack aircraft will require:

- a. An agile aircraft.

- b. An agile missile.

- c. A helmet mounted sight.

In response to tasking by the Joint Advanced Strike Technologies Program in the summer of 1994, the X-31 Program undertook a Quasi-Tailless Experiment.

The objectives of the X-31 QT experiment were to produce a design database for advanced strike aircraft and to demonstrate the feasibility of tailless flight using thrust vectoring. This was then broken down further into Phase I; which sought to validate the X-31 simulation model for QT flight, and then extend that model by analysis to generic tailless concepts. Phase II objectives were to define and demonstrate flight test maneuvers typical of those required for an advanced tailless strike fighter that employs thrust vectoring for directional stability augmentation.

2. THE X-31A AIRCRAFT

The X-31 aircraft was designed and built by North American Aircraft/Rockwell International and Deutsche Aerospace. The aircraft has an empty weight of 11,800 lb., and a maximum takeoff weight of 16,100 lb., of which 4,100 lb. is fuel. The X-31 utilizes tricycle landing gear from the F-16 aircraft, with wheel and wheel brake assemblies from a Cessna Citation.

The cockpit and canopy are largely made up from components supplied from the US Navy F/A-18. The ejection seat is a SJU-5, the Heads-Up Display (HUD) and Digital Display

Indicator (DDI) are also from the F/A-18 series aircraft.

The X-31 is powered by a single General Electric GE-F404-400 engine which generates 10,800 lb. of thrust at military and 16,000 lb. of thrust at maximum afterburner. This is the same engine installed on both the F/A-18A-D and F117 aircraft

The aircraft is a canard design, with severely swept main wings, of the double delta design. Leading edge flaps, and trailing edge flaps comprise the remaining high lift devices installed.

The Thrust Vectoring Vanes (TVV's) are of a German design and constructed from carbon

fiber composites. The TVV's actuators are located within the exterior mold line of the aircraft, at the twelve, four and eight o'clock positions. The Vanes themselves are located in the free stream, and are connected to the aircraft via a hinge point and to the TVV actuator rod end. The TVV's travel through 350 degrees of travel into the jet plume. The TVV's are capable of operating in unison, singly and as speed brake augments, in the speed brake augment mode, TVV's 2 & 3 (4 and 8 o'clock positions) may be positioned up to 60° into the relative wind. An algorithm resident in the flight controls software prevents thrust vectoring vane to thrust vectoring vane contact at TVV deflections

greater than 25° . Jet plume deflection is software limited to 16° maximum.

Primary Flight Controls - The primary flight controls hardware were designed by Rockwell International, and the flight control software was designed by Mr. Hermann Beh, and Georg Hofinger, Deutsche Aerospace .

The control stick is center mounted. The stick pitch command commands alpha at low dynamic pressures and Nz (normal acceleration) at high dynamic pressures. The breakout force from the neutral position is +/- 1 pound Total stick travel is 2.96 inches forward, and 4.44 inches in the pull direction for 7.4 inches total travel. Of the 4.44 inches of travel in the pull direction, 2.96 inches is used for conventional flight, and 1.48 inches is used with a stick force detent for post-stall maneuvers. The stick force is linear (5 pounds per inch) throughout the total deflection range. Pitch commands are quad-redundant, and are supplied to the four Flight Control Computers (FCC's). Three signals are used directly by the FCC's, with one signal in reserve as a tie breaker. The flight control computers actively limit the maximum commands as a function of available control power. Additionally the X-31 flight control system incorporates inertial and engine gyroscopic coupling compensation.

Lateral stick displacement is 3.0 inches left and right which commands flight path axis roll rate. The lateral stick force gradient is linear at 4.0 pounds per inch throughout the entire deflection range.

The control stick feel system is implemented using mechanical springs, and the position feedback is measured by potentiometers.

The rudders are force sensing units from the F-16 aircraft, and command sideslip. Artificial feel is provided by springs, and the

quad redundant signal is supplied to the FCC's to command beta. At angles of attack above 45° the rudder is faired to the trail position, and all high alpha flight above this point is then essentially tailless, with all directional stability and control supplied from the thrust vectoring system.

The aircraft is unstable in pitch, with the flight control computers providing artificial stability. Directional stability is slightly positive in the $0-25^{\circ}$ AOA region, with beta and stability axis yaw rate feedback provided for increased stability.

The canards operate in unison to control pitch, and travel through $+10^{\circ}$ to -70° of pitch, referenced to the aircraft waterline. High lift devices are composed of the canards, leading edge flaps (LEF), and trailing edge flaps (TEF). The ailerons are conventional in design and function.

3. QUASI-TAILLESS INFLIGHT SIMULATION

The Quasi-Tailless (QT) mode was mechanized by incorporating the following features into the flight control system. The normal augmentation to the rudder for directional stabilization and control is shut off, and a destabilization feedback is introduced to the rudder and aileron. Destabilization is accomplished by feeding back roll rate, yaw rate and beta to the rudder and aileron to obtain the lateral/directional flying qualities of a reduced/tailless X-31 by,

- Matching the eigenvalues of a Quasi-Tailless and tailless X-31 (low order system).

- Analysis of a high-order system by including all dynamic elements determines the level of instability actually demonstrated.

Restabilization is then mechanized by redistribution of the required control power to the Thrust Vectoring system.

Various destabilization gain sets are inflight selectable. These are assigned to "QT Indices" which correspond to percent of vertical tail removed.

In QT, the maximum roll rate, roll acceleration command, beta and beta dot are limited as a function of estimated thrust which equates to available control power.

Noteworthy is that in the QT mode, the partial use of rudder can be simulated inflight. Automatic safety disengagement occurs if specified envelope parameters are exceeded (i.e. beta, N_z , V_t , etc.).

In the Quasi-Tailless mode, the maximum angle of thrust deflection is 16° , with a maximum thrust deflection rate of 45° per second, based on a software limit of 60° per second for the thrust vectoring vanes.

To calculate the control power utilized during the maneuvers, the "utilization value" was always the peak value recorded for the maneuver - with no attempt to reduce sharp spikes.

The Quasi-Tailless Mode is selected via the Status Test Panel on the left lower

vertical panel, see figure 2.

The pilot accesses the flight test operational flight program via the Status/Test Panel, by stepping through the displays with the left and right arrows. Once the proper data page or sub-page is selected, he then enters his selection with the "VERIFY" pushbutton. In this manner, the Quasi-Tailless Mode, and desired QT Index are selected. Once selected the Status/Test Panel and HUD both show "QT 0-6" indicating to pilot and control room that the system is selected and ready.

QT Index:	% Vertical Tail Removed:
0	0
1	30
2	40
3	50
4	60
5	70
6	80

Figure 2. Status/Test Panel

The QT Mode is activated via the select switch on the front of the throttle, see figure 3. Once the QT select switch has been pressed the Status/Test Panel and HUD both show "QT 0-6 ENGAGED." This provides positive confirmation to the pilot and control room of

the aircraft operating mode.

QT mode deselection may occur for a variety of parameters, as well as upon pilot deselection. The pilot has two methods of deselecting the QT mode while in flight. The

first is via the same QT select switch on the throttle, the second method being with the paddle switch on the lower forward part of the control stick, see figure: 4, below.

4. FLIGHT TEST

QT Mode Envelope Expansion Phase I was pursued aggressively, and much of the simulation and analysis were underway well before the official signing of the program tasking in Washington D.C. This enabled us to maximize our two most precious assets, our outstanding individuals working on the team and time. The team undertook the challenge of implementing a QT control law into the existing X-31 flight control system and to modify the TV system from basically single point optimization (post-stall at maximum afterburner) to the takeoff and landing phase and the demanding ground attack environment. Two factors were to prove ongoing challenges, accurately determining the jet exhaust plume area in the vicinity of the thrust vectoring vanes (TVV's or paddles), and the expanded flight envelope down to 2,200' MSL vice 14,000' MSL from the CIC testing.

Determining the exact jet plume location was a time consuming exercise. This required repeated test points at predicted test conditions, during which the TVV's were individually, slowly moved from their stowed position into the jet plume. As each TVV was incrementally moved in by the pilot, the control room monitored TVV Ptotal (measured by a

probe located on the aft portion of each TVV) and sensed load on the TVV actuator. These two parameters were used to gauge the location of the jet plume, and TVV deflection required to achieve the jet plume deflection for a given commanded control moment command.

The original Operational Flight Controls Program (OFP) utilized for the QT inflight simulation was OFP 119. The flying qualities observed were generally quite good, but there were notable handling qualities deficiencies. The aircraft tended to build up beta during mild maneuvering and in particular during full lateral stick deflection aileron rolls and bank to bank rolls. Quasi-tailless inflight simulation often resulted in exceeding beta limits for the aforementioned maneuvers and inputs. Analysis revealed that there was a marked delta between commanded jet plume deflection and actual, see figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Commanded Jet Deflection vs. Actual, OFP 119

Concurrently, the TVV actuators on ship 1 were removed for modification. Ground based simulation showed unacceptable handling qualities due to hard-over TVV failure into the jet plume. The solution was to modify the TVV actuators by removing a restrictor in the return hydraulic path. This restrictor was originally placed in the actuators to smooth their scheduling, and was found to also increase the time required to remove a TVV from the jet plume in hard-over type failures.

This discrepancy required another update to the jet plume area in the flight control software tables, and TVV deflection required for commanded jet plume deflection commanded portions of the TV Effectiveness tables.

OFP 120A Once the update to the OFP and modified TVV actuators were available, they were loaded and installed into ship 1. Flight testing of the revised Operational Flight Controls Program (OFP) 120A was begun in late November of 1994. Mr. Fred Knox of NAA/RI, Mr. Karl-Heinz Lang and Captain Loria then began flying the envelope expansion matrix which they developed.

The flight test results of OFP 120A with the updated TVV Effectiveness tables

are presented below in figure 6.

The new configuration was a success. The aircraft exhibited delightful handling qualities throughout the envelope!

Due to the lack of time available, envelope expansion efforts were directed to two very specific areas:

1. Power Approach configuration, landing gear down, high lift devices engaged, on-speed (~170 KCAS) to 220 KCAS, from the surface through 10,000' AGL..
2. Cruise configuration, from 360-420 KCAS, 1,000' AGL through 10,000' AGL.

Due to the limited scope of this experiment, classic and new flight test techniques were utilized to open this envelope. Flight test techniques investigating primarily the

Figure: 6. Commanded Jet Deflection vs. Actual, OFP 120A

directional static and dynamic stability were used, for throttle fixed and throttle free conditions. The throttle fixed test points were employed as both baseline to determine the level of success of OFP 120B and as a handling qualities reference for the throttle free handling qualities.

During investigation of the various configurations for PA, it was observed that the destabilizing effect of landing gear, landing gear doors, high lift devices (TEF and canards), and speed brakes had a synergistic effect. That is the sum of the three was greater than the arithmetic sum of their individual effects. This can be observed in

figure 7.

The QT cruise (CR) flight testing for the Air-to-Ground phase of testing, the envelope expansion was relatively straight forward. Predominantly classic flight test techniques were utilized for QT CR envelope expansion testing. These included doublets in all axis, bank-to-bank rolls, aileron rolls, level turns, N_z captures and loaded rolls. These maneuvers were then linked, together, at safe altitudes to parallel the carrier approaches and air-to-ground maneuvers. Once safely conducted, in a piecewise fashion, the entire maneuvers were flown at altitude, and then flown progressively lower to the final test

altitudes.

For all envelope expansion, and data missions, no attempts were made to smooth, or average out any spikes in parameters. This was done to assure that there was adequate control power and bandwidth to perform all maneuvers and tasks.

Precision Approach Flight Test - The field carrier approach task was chosen for Quasi-Tailless flight tests because it provided a high gain, mission relatable task. Characteristics of the carrier approach which make it a challenging task for the flight control system are

1. The task is very high gain, requiring precise control of airplane angle-of-attack (AOA), glide slope, and lineup.

2. The carrier approach task is mission representative in that it is used by all Navy fixed wing aircraft to recover aboard the aircraft carrier both day and night, as well as ashore.

3. The low airspeeds associated with landing combined with the requirements for precise control of the airplane result in large control surface deflection and large control moment requirements, especially for roll control. This leads to additional control requirements to minimize yaw.

4. Carrier approaches are typically

flown using a "backside" method where the throttle is used to maintain glide slope, and nose attitude to control airspeed. This "backside" method results in dynamic throttle movement of varying amplitude, and frequency.

The ITO solicited the Navy's Shipboard Suitability and Landing Systems Department of the Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division, Patuxent River to develop tasks which would be mission representative of the carrier approach and to assist in the flight testing of these tasks. The X31 airplane presented specific challenges to this evaluation.

Carrier Approach Description - The typical carrier approach landing pattern is shown in figure 8. The carrier approach commences from a 800 ft level break turn which

Figure: 8. Carrier Approach

decelerates the aircraft. On the downwind leg the airplane landing configuration is set and the airplane is established at 600 ft, 1.5 nm abeam of the ship at the desired approach AOA. A constant angle-of-bank descending approach turn is commenced to enable roll-out on final approach 0.75 nm behind the carrier on a 3.5 degree. glide slope, lined up on the centerline, and at the desired approach AOA. During the approach, the pilot maintains tight control of glide slope by modulating thrust, and angle of attack by adjusting pitch attitude, while maintaining the aircraft on centerline. Aircraft typically touchdown at a rate of descent of 600 to 800 fpm (10 to 13 fps). Glide slope indication is presented to the pilot using the Fresnel Lens Optical Landing System (FLOLS) (figure 9).

The desired glide slope is indicated by the lighted vertical cell being aligned with the horizontal reference lights. Above or below nominal glide slope is indicated by a higher or lower cell being lighted respectively.

The landing criteria is dictated by the landing zone of the carrier, performance capability of the arresting gear, and structural design criteria of the airplane. Tight control of glide slope, AOA, and lineup result in

1. Safer landing operations due to a more predictable approach path.
2. Enhanced operational capability as shipboard recovery wind-over-deck (WOD) requirements can be reduced.
3. Lighter airplane structural weight

Figure: 9. Fresnel Lens Optical Landings System (FLOLS) Layout

This visual landing aid consists of a column of five vertical lights or cells (with a total projected field-of-view of 1.7 degree.) bisected with a row of twelve horizontal reference lights.

as the airplane can be designed to tighter landing tolerances. To illustrate the small landing area, a aircraft carrier deck layout is shown in figure 10.

Figure: 10. Carrier Deck Layout

To maximize operational capability any of the four arresting gear wires can be targeted as the desired touchdown point. Therefore to ensure adequate clearance over the ramp (aft end of the flight deck) at glide slopes of 3.5 degree. to 4.0 degree., the airplane must be able land in a 80 ft long zone. Due to the limited width of the flight deck, the airplane must land in a zone 20 ft wide. This width may have to be reduced for airplanes with large wingspans.

To obtain this in a stabilized approach typical desired criteria for a carrier approach are as follows:

1. Maintain glide slope within 1/2 cell (e.g. 0.17 degree.)
2. Maintain approach AOA within 1/2 degree.
3. Maintain landing area centerline +/- 5 ft of centerline

QT PA Challenges - Conducting a meaningful field carrier landing evaluation of the QT flight control system in the X-31 was challenging because the X-31 was not

designed with the requirement for precision approach. Therefore, several airplane characteristics made the field carrier approach tasks difficult. These characteristics are as follows:

1. The X-31 has an approach speed of approximately 170 KCAS. The high approach speed results in high closure speeds and less time for corrections on final approach. The high approach speed also resulted in high sink speeds (>1000 fpm) at normal field carrier approach FLOLS settings of 3.25 degrees This in turn resulted in low approach power settings and poor waveoff (go-around) performance.

2. The delta wing configuration resulted in a normal X-31 approach AOA of 12 degrees This high approach AOA resulted in barely acceptable over the nose field-of-view (FOV). The FOV limitation prevented the test team from raising the approach AOA further, in attempts to lower the approach airspeed.

3. The approach configuration also had relatively low drag, resulting in low

approach power settings. Low power settings make precision glide slope control more difficult due to slower engine response characteristics. These power settings also provided a challenge to the design of the QT control laws as vectored thrust is the only means for directional control, with QT engaged. A QT automatic disengage was placed in the software when PLA dropped below 55 degrees in order to avoid QT operation at insufficient thrust levels.

4. The control laws were not optimized for precision approach.

QT PA Test Methods - The initial plan for the QT PA evaluation was to conduct the tests using a two phase approach. The first phase was to conduct a verification of the precision

PA formation tasks were initially conducted at 10,000 and 5,000 ft MSL. These initial altitudes were selected to evaluate PA flying qualities in a high gain task while in a relatively safe environment (i.e. well away from the ground). Based upon recommendations from LCdr Robert Niewoehner, SATS a JAST Flight Mechanics Team Member, a slot position task was developed to investigate the directional stability of the X-31 QT configuration. Two formation positions, slot and standard F/A-18 parade, were used for the evaluation. The positions are shown in figure 11.

Each formation task was then broken down into a gross acquisition task and a fine tracking task. The gross acquisition task was performed in two fashions. In the first and

Figure: 11. Formation Positions

approach tasks in the airplane basic control system. Phase II was the actual evaluation of the QT control system. The tasks used for this evaluation included PA formation and field carrier approaches.

less productive method, the test pilot flying the X-31 would capture the desired position/parameters from a looser position.

This proved to be less than optimal because of the test pilots a priori knowledge of when to

initiate the correction, and his starting position, etc. The second and more productive method was adopted based on recommendations from Mr. Rogers Smith, NASA Dryden Chief Test pilot and X-31 test pilot. Mr. Rogers Smith recommended that the lead aircraft utilize step inputs (appropriate for the formation being flown) to present the test pilot with deviations requiring gross re-acquisition and fine tracking of the formation parameters. This proved to yield consistently higher pilot gains, which were reflected in the observed frequency of pilot stick and throttle inputs.

The lead pilot would perform mild maneuvering in pitch and roll followed by step pitch inputs (+/- 5 degree.) with the X-31 in the parade position; or step roll inputs (+/- 10 degree.) with the X-31 in the slot position. These step maneuvers by the lead airplane resulted in unpredicted deviations from the desired position, with the task being to re-acquire the desired position as quickly as possible. Desired /adequate criteria for maintaining the slot and parade positions were +/- 1 ft / +/- 5 ft in all axis, respectively.

Once the formation tasks were successfully completed the primary task of field carrier approaches could than be conducted. Field carrier approaches were conducted using the Navy Fresnel Lens Optical Landing System. Due to the high approach speed of the X-31 a glide slope setting of 2.75 degrees was initially selected to obtain a sink speed closer to the normal sink speeds for carrier approaches. Nominal and offset (intentional deviations) approaches were to be flown under the control of a Navy Landing Signals Officer (LSO). The LSO provides feedback to the pilot and is a safety observer during all portions of the approach. Intentional deviations in glide slope and lineup were corrected at different points in the approach. All approaches were terminated in a waveoff

initiated at a minimum altitude of 100 ft as the landing gear on the X-31 were not structurally adequate for carrier type landings. The test pilots for this portion of the evaluation were Mr. Fred Knox and Captain Loria, who were experienced X-31 pilots with carrier aviation backgrounds. The pilot's were to rate the flying qualities of the X-31 using the tolerances shown above. Other than the change to the glide slope, no other changes were made from the typical carrier approach pattern.

QT PA Initial Results / Task Modification - The PA formation tasks resulted in high gain pilot inputs to capture and maintain position, particularly in the slot position. Both evaluation pilots felt that the tasks and criteria were good for evaluating the QT mode. No modification of the task was required during this phase of the evaluation.

During the precision approach phase there were several obstacles that readily became apparent as follows:

1. Glide slope control was very difficult. The primary reasons were the low approach power setting and very sensitive pitch axis. The low approach power settings resulted in poor power response requiring the pilot to use longitudinal stick to help make glide slope corrections. The sensitivity in the pitch axis caused the pilot to frequently over control the nose resulting in deviations above and below the desired glide slope. Once deviated from the desired glide slope, the evaluation pilots were rarely able to recapture glide slope and typically rated the handling qualities as very objectionable while attempting to perform this task. It was readily apparent that the task of maintaining glide slope with lateral deviations only was sufficiently high gain to produce the pilot inputs needed for this evaluation.

2. The low power settings required to maintain glide slope also posed another problem for the QT evaluation. The QT control laws featured an automatic disengage feature (to the basic mode) when the Power Lever Angle (PLA) was moved below 55 degrees. During these initial approaches large changes in PLA were seen with the minimum PLA dropping below 55 degree. on almost every approach.

3. The high approach airspeed reduced the time during final approach by up to 45% when compared to carrier based aircraft. A typical carrier approach groove length (time established on final approach) was 15 to 18 sec. The X-31 groove length was approximately 10 sec. This short amount of time established on final resulted in less time for corrections.

4. The field-of-view (FOV) was acceptable at the approach AOA of 12 degrees. Approaches were conducted at 12.5 and 13 degrees angle of attack in attempts to reduce the X-31 sink rate, approach speed, and increase the average power setting. We were precluded from higher approach angles of attack due to field of view problems, and unacceptable visual distortion through the windscreen at these higher angles of attack.

5. The approaches that were normally flown at the conclusion of previous X-31 test missions were non-precision approaches to a flared landing. This, combined with touch and go landings being prohibited by the X-31 flight manual resulted in a low number of total X-31 landings for the test team pilots.

Revised QT PA Tasks - Based on the results of the initial flight testing, the test team evaluated the carrier approach tasks to see if the approach task could be made more

mission relatable in workload and performance while still providing valid data

Another proposed change was to add drag inducing devices to the airplane. Increasing the drag would increase approach power settings, and improve aircraft response characteristics. Approaches were flown with speed brakes retracted and extended during baseline flights, using only the thrust vectoring, no QT. New drag device modifications were not feasible in the short period of time available to conduct the tests. Based upon the results from baseline testing, it was decided to use speed brakes extended for the actual QT data flights. This presented the additional problem of the non-linear contributions of landing gear and doors, high lift devices and speed brakes to the aircraft's $C_{n\beta}$. All of these combined had a greater destabilizing effect than their individual components had indicated. Therefore, for the QT Precision Glide slope testing a QT Index of 3 (versus QT Index of 4) was selected which resulted in achieving, and surpassing our targeted level of directional instability $C_{n\beta} = -0.0017$.

Changes to the approach task were as follows:

- The approach glide slope was reduced further to 2.5 degrees. This change would reduced airplane sink rate to approximately 700 fpm and increased the approach power setting.

- The final approach was lengthened from 0.75 nm to approximately 1.5 nm. Corrections for intentional deviations from the approach would then be conducted at 1.5 nm (start) to 1.0 nm (in-the-middle) positions, based upon radio calls from the LSO. Lengthening the approach gave the pilot approximately the same amount of time on final approach as that in a typical carrier day, VMC approach (18 to 20 sec).

- A flight test throttle detent was developed, tested and installed at a PLA of 56 degrees. The detent served as a flight test QT flight idle stop, and gave the pilot an indication of proximity to the QT PLA disengage position.

- A flight test AOA indexer was installed on the left side of the Heads Up Display (HUD). This gave the test pilots a usable indicator of AOA closer in his scan pattern. The AOA indexer is the primary source of AOA data for most carrier airplanes.

- The test team decided that glide slope control was challenging enough without intentional deviations. Therefore, only deviations in lineup would be conducted as the lateral-directional axis was of primary importance during the QT evaluation.

QT PA Evaluation Results - Formation tasks and precision approaches were conducted up to a QT index of 3 (CnB of -.0035). The slot formation tasks proved to be very good at exercising the lateral-directional control axis as aggressive lateral displacements and captures could be conducted. The side-by-side relationship of the parade position did not allow for these aggressive lateral maneuvers, but was useful in determining sensitivity to pitch inputs, low power lever angles, and slower engine response times. To compare the difference in flying qualities, maneuvers were performed with and without QT engaged. There were no differences observed in flying qualities between the basic airplane (TV on), and the X-31 airplane with a QT index of up to 3!

Approaches were also flown up to a QT index of 3. Lateral deviations from runway centerline were flown on the off-nominal approaches, with aggressive corrections to recapture centerline. The lateral

offset/centerline capture tasks were predominantly flown 50 ft. left or right of runway centerline, down to 350 ft. AGL with centerline capture initiated then, upon the LSO's radio call. This centerline capture task is performed while maintaining AOA (+/- 1/2 ball is desired, +/- 1 ball adequate), and glideslope (+/- 1/2 ball is desired, +/- 1 ball adequate).

Although the difficulties in glide slope control and the sensitivity in pitch were still apparent, the pilot's were still able to separate the lateral-directional axis for evaluation. As in the formation tasks, approaches were performed with and without QT engaged and there were no discernible differences in flying qualities in the QT mode. Cooper Harper (CH) Handling Qualities Ratings (HQR's) were predominantly 4's and 5's, for level two flying qualities. It is important to point out that these are normal representative CH HQR's for current USN/USMC fixed wing, jet carrier aircraft performing the same task. There were no lateral directional oscillations, Dutch roll or objectionable flying qualities noted. There was no pilot observable change in flying qualities between the basic aircraft with TV or QT index of 3 engaged! As seen in figure 12, there was adequate control power available while performing this task as compared to the basic X-31 aircraft, with TV on performing the same task.

Power settings during the approach averaged 5 degree. above the QT auto-disengage setting of 55 degrees. The auto-disengage feature occurred during a few approaches when the pilot inadvertently moved the throttle below the throttle detent. There were no transients or changes to the flying qualities noted during these unintentional disengages. Initially, the pilot's first realization that QT had disengaged was a call from the control room! During both the formation tasks and the approaches that incorporated lateral offsets, up to 1/2 of

the available thrust vectoring capability was utilized.

Testing in turbulence (all tests were conducted in smooth air) would have caused more thrust vectoring control power to be used. No cross axis coupling with thrust vectoring was apparent, and there were no directional instabilities.

Even with the extremely low power settings, there was sufficient thrust vectoring capability to provide directional control without any apparent degradation in flying qualities. Two dedicated test missions were flown in support of this phase of testing, two flights were utilized for task validation/refinement and to

establish the baseline performance of the aircraft. thirteen flights were flown while expanding the envelope for the QT PA testing.

Quasi-Tailless Power Approach: Conclusions & Recommendations - Although the field carrier landing approach task was modified, it still provided an excellent, high gain task for evaluating this flight control system in the power approach configuration.

An important item to remember for this evaluation, was that the team was not evaluating the X-31 for carrier suitability but was evaluating a part of the flight control system in an environment similar in pilot workload and flight control system demands to the carrier approach. This was a first step in evaluating the capability of thrust vectoring and the feasibility of tailless configurations in the carrier approach environment.

This evaluation also showed the flexibility of the X-31 as a test bed for integration of thrust vectoring into operational airplanes. This airplane although never designed for precision approach capability was still able to fly in that environment and provide volumes of high quality data. The X-31 test team was also able to adapt the demands of conducting test flights in the low altitude environment of the approach to landing.

Ground Attack Flight Test - Air-to-Ground Tasks: In support of the goals and objectives supplied to the X-31 International Test Organization from the JAST Program, MR. Fred Knox NAA/RI, Major Quirin Kim Luftwaffe, and Captain Loria USMC, selected the following three mission representative tasks.

The first was a 45° Dive Attack, with altitude and throttle position selected to deny the simulated hand-held surface-to-air missile (SAM) and mobile SAM threat. A base leg was flown at 18,000' AGL and 250 KCAS. Roll-in was adjusted to achieve the desired dive angle, and the throttle was positioned at the QT Cruise (CR) flight test idle stop (63° PLA) to approximate worst case conditions for the flight controls/thrust vectoring system. The target would then be tracked to a simulated release altitude of 12,000' AGL/400 KCAS, at which time a 4-4.5 N_Z pull-off would be conducted with the throttle still at 63° PLA (see figure 13). Gross acquisition task desired and adequate performance criteria were target acquisition within the outer HUD sight ring (25 mils radius) with no overshoots, and one overshoot respectively. Fine tracking desired and adequate performance criteria were target tracking within the inner sight ring, no overshoots, and one overshoot respectively.

The second task was a 15° Dive delivery against NASA's Adaptable Target Lighting Array System (ATLAS). The ATLAS is a ground based system of high intensity lights that are utilized for closed loop evaluation of aircraft handling qualities deficiencies. Typically, the ATLAS lighting array is utilized for an open loop gross acquisition task, on the turn from base to final attack profile, during which all the lights are on bright and steady. Then the pilot transitions to fine tracking of point targets as the nine high intensity lights cycle individually, in an apparently random fashion. This task was modeled after air-to-ground strafe patterns, and also served to examine the X-31 QT closed loop handling qualities with a well defined task and performance criteria. Gross acquisition task desired and adequate performance criteria were target acquisition within the outer HUD sight ring (25 mils

radius) with no overshoots, and one overshoot respectively. Fine tracking desired and adequate performance criteria were target tracking within the inner sight ring, no overshoots, and one overshoot respectively.

The ATLAS 15° Dive Attacks were flown from a pattern using a 4,000' AGL/350 KCAS downwind and base legs. From the base leg the chase aircraft would activate the ATLAS (e.g. turning the lights on). The X-31 would then execute a 4 g turn to grossly acquire the ATLAS array within the HUD field of view. Again for this task, the throttle was set at the flight test idle stop (63° PLA) to approximate worst case conditions for the flight controls/thrust vectoring system. For this gross acquisition task, no overshoots were desired, and one overshoot was adequate performance criteria.

Once the ATLAS lights began their pre-programmed, apparently random, cycling of individual light sources the pilots conducted fine tracking of the lights. This light source then served as a point target for the simulated strafe delivery, with 5-7 target shifts per run. Runs were conducted from approximately 4,000' AGL down to 1,000' AGL at 400 KCAS

It is important to note that the pilots were free to aggressively track the targets as their background and training dictated. Major Kim utilized predominantly aggressive step type stick inputs, whereas Captain Loria utilized slightly smoother stick inputs, but also used rudder pedal inputs to correct for any lateral pipper placement error.

The third task was modeled after a low-level ingress, to a "Pop" attack with simulated release of high drag munitions. The ingress was flown at 1,000' AGL/400 KCAS.

The "Pop" point was adjusted to allow each pilot to execute a loaded roll. This loaded roll was comprised of a 4 N_z capture, a bank angle, 30° heading change, and a 30° pitch capture. Once in the climb, the aircraft was unloaded to 0.5 N_z at the pull-down point of 2,500' AGL, and aggressively rolled to place the lift vector on the target. From this position the aircraft was longitudinally pulled to achieve gross acquisition of the target within the HUD, at which time the aircraft was again partially unloaded and rolled to wings level, erect flight. The target was then tracked for approximately 15 seconds before simulating release at 1,500' AGL/400 KCAS. After pausing to allow for simulated weapon release, the aircraft was recovered from the dive using a 4.5 N_z longitudinal pull, until the velocity vector was above the horizon.

Gross acquisition task desired and adequate performance criteria were target acquisition within the outer HUD sight ring with no overshoots, and one overshoot respectively. Fine tracking desired and adequate performance criteria were target tracking within the inner sight ring, no overshoots, and one overshoot respectively.

QT Air-to-Ground FLight Test - Thirteen flights were flown expanding the envelope for this phase of testing. Two data missions were flown initially, followed by debriefing and data analysis.

The flights commenced with normal basic flight control laws for takeoff and departure to the test area. Once established in the test area, QT CR = 4 was selected, which corresponded to 60% vertical tail removed, and a $C_{n\beta} = -0.0012$.

During the 45° Dive Attack, handling qualities deficiencies noted were sluggish response, slow roll rates, and a general lack of

crispness to the aircraft response. During fine tracking in the 45° dives, both pilots observed small but noticeable and objectionable engine gyroscopic effects following longitudinal piper placement corrections. Dive recoveries were normal with no objectionable flying qualities noted. Cooper-Harper (CH) Handling Qualities Ratings (HQR's) for the gross acquisition were 5's and fine tracking was 3's and 4's with pilot comments as noted above.

The ATLAS 15° Dive Attacks resulted in again deficiencies being noted for sluggish response in roll, and slow roll rate. Longitudinal response was fine, although sensitive. Gross acquisition desired criteria was achieved forty percent of the time. Pilots cited the sluggish roll response as the main factor in inability to repeatably achieve desired gross acquisitions, with CH HQR's of 5. At the slightly higher N_z 's encountered in the 15° dive, no engine gyroscopic effects were observed. Fine tracking resulted in achievement of desired performance criteria, with CH HQR's of 3.

Low-level Ingress to Pop Attack further demonstrated the limitations of the aircraft configuration, and operating restrictions. Again the roll response was found to be sluggish, with roll rate also too slow. The longitudinal axis was sensitive to small pilot inputs, especially at and approaching 400 KCAS. CH HQR's were 5 for gross acquisition and 3 for fine tracking.

QT Air-to-Ground FLight Test: Initial Results, Analysis & Action - Both Major Kim and Captain Loria found the aircraft capable of performing all assigned tasks. Deficient was the ability to aggressively fly these maneuvers in a fully mission representative fashion. Both pilots for this test portion found the aircraft only adequately performing

the tasks, with improvements required to satisfy the mission applicability portion of the test.

With this in mind, Captain Loria and Major Kim called a meeting of the flight controls team. The group began analyzing the handling qualities deficiencies noted, and maneuver limitations imposed by the engineers. It was determined that the lateral stick deflection limits were unnecessarily high. They were originally placed at only half lateral stick deflection due to the beta build-up observed during 360° aileron rolls while expanding the envelope. However, to perform the air-to-ground tasks, the largest rolling maneuvers would require only approximately 135° angle of bank change. To correct for the observed sluggish roll response and rates, the power was allowed to be modulated, as per a normal ground attack profile. This affected the roll mode time constant, and steady state roll rates due to the fact that they varied based upon the QT index engaged, as well as the throttle position (PLA) and control moment generated. An impromptu fixed base simulation study was then performed, with immediate and noticeable improvements in aircraft response, predictability and task performance. The team was able to come to a consensus on revised limits on control inputs, and throttle settings during the maneuvers. This directly resulted in the greater mission representative execution of the tasks on the following day.

It is very important to observe that a paramount objective had been realized on this first day. That given worst case throttle settings the aircraft was able to perform its mission, though not with level one flying qualities. Worst case control power margins and engine response had been aggressively tested with less than 50% of the available control power margin being used.

QT Air-to-Ground Flight Test: Revised Tasks - The maneuvers were modified to allow the pilot to use up to military rated thrust for the gross acquisition task, as is normally done in actual air-to-ground deliveries. This enables the pilot to maintain his energy state while aggressively maneuvering his aircraft. For us this maintained our energy state but also gave us the control power, and increased roll rates, and decreased roll mode time constants to achieve improved performance.

Once wings level in the dives, the game plan was to "stand the throttle up" or pull the power back to mid-range. Tactically this is done to reduce infrared signature, and allow longer tracking time in the dive, as release parameters are reached slower. This increased our available thrust from 3,000 lb. to 4,000 lb. and it was this marginal increase that achieved enough control moment to remove the engine gyroscopic effects.

Revised QT Air-to-Ground Results - The following day, two additional test missions were scheduled to further investigate the Quasi-Tailless, Cruise, Air-to-Ground applications. Flights 1-288 and 1-289 were flown at QT CR Index = 4 to investigate the revised tasks, and observe any changes in aircraft handling qualities.

The handling qualities and aircraft performance of the demanding air-to-ground tasks was markedly improved for the better.

As seen in figure 13 below, there was more than adequate control power supplied by the thrust vectoring system for the "Pop" attack flown using the revisions. As seen in the plot below, with the basic aircraft, TV on, there is negligible control power required by the basic X-31.

However, in QT CR = 4, there was significant control power required as depicted by the magnitude and duration of jet deflection. For this one maneuver, roughly 33% of the total control power was still available. The other maneuvers typically showed 50% of available control power remaining. The control rates were evaluated as adequate, and the sideslip buildup (2°) was the same as for the basic aircraft!

Level one flying qualities were achieved for fine tracking tasks for all three deliveries.

Gross acquisition tasks were still level two flying qualities, but for pilot workload, and compensation required, not for failure to achieve desired performance criteria. "Thrust vectoring and a QT index = 4 are suitable for these tasks and mission based on this limited investigation."

It is believed that shorter roll mode time constants and higher roll rates are achievable in this configuration. This is postulated given the conservative nature of the initial values tested, and the typical angle of bank changes used for this mission. For angle of bank changes greater than those observed here, many solutions are possible (and not limited to) flight manual limiting of lateral stick deflection for angle of bank changes greater than 180° , and a predictive correction for beta, based upon flight conditions and commanded roll rate. The later possible solution would have the advantage of not having the inherent time lag associated with sensing the beta and beta dot, then processing that signal, generating a command to correct for it and so on.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based upon the results of this limited experiment, tailless aircraft designs are suitable for the strike fighter mission for the US armed forces.

Less than 50% of the available control power was required for directional control during the demanding carrier approaches at Quasi-Tailless Power Approach Index of 3 ($C_{n\beta} = -0.0035$), with and without the lateral offset/centerline capture task.

Less than 50% of the available control power was required for directional control during the

demanding air-to-ground simulated deliveries at a Quasi-Tailless Cruise Index of 3 ($C_{n\beta} = -0.0017$).

In the ground attack mission the tailless configuration was found to be mission suitable, so long as mission representative thrust levels during maneuvers were maintained.

Given the objective of a tailless design when initially designing an aircraft, the basic airframe can be designed with proper static and dynamic stability.

It is believed that shorter roll mode time constants and higher roll rates are achievable in this configuration. This is postulated given the conservative nature of the initial values tested, and the typical angle of bank changes used for this mission. For angle of bank changes greater than those observed here, many solutions are possible (and not limited to) flight manual limiting of lateral stick deflection for angle of bank changes greater than 180° , and a predictive correction for beta, based upon flight conditions and commanded roll rate. The later possible solution would have the advantage of not having the inherent time lag associated with sensing the beta and beta dot, then processing that signal, generating a command to correct for it and so on.

Tailless configurations bring many advantages and design challenges with it.

Advantages:

1.) Weight savings, which equates to increased range, performance, payload and manufacturing savings.

2.) Reduced form drag.

3.) Reduced trim drag for the directional axis and longitudinally (assuming axisymmetric thrust vectoring).

4.) Design lends itself to low observable radar and visual designs.

6. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS FOR FUTURE TAILLESS AIRCRAFT

Reduced tail and tailless tactical aircraft designs are feasible today with existing technology and hardware.

To build an efficient tailless or reduced tail aircraft requires working from a clean sheet of paper, blending all facets of airframe, powerplant and control system design against the performance and flying qualities design objectives. The obvious design factors such as wing sweep, dihedral, and planform need to be optimized to achieve the target directional stability, as well as levels of low observables.

For tactical applications, the degree of low observable can be balanced against the required amount of aircraft tail, and control system design. For example, for a close air support type aircraft, which will come well within the visual engagement zones of ground based infantry to deliver its ordnance - has significantly different design considerations than a strategic asset. The role or mission will then (as now) be the driver for the aircraft design.

As proven in this limited investigation, a directionally unstable aircraft could be flown in the demanding carrier aviation environment. To further improve the aircraft's recovery characteristics, and decrease the demands on the thrust vectoring system, a deployable vertical tail could be used for landing or other flight regimes.

As utilized in this application, single engine designs lend themselves readily to this application. Twin engine designs offer further benefits to the aircraft designer.

In twin engine applications, the redundancy in propulsion, electrical and hydraulic systems increases the overall system safety. Also, twin engine design configurations are more capable in cases of heavy stores loadings, in particular when large asymmetric loadings result. In these cases the thrust can be applied to minimize the effects on the roll axis, as well as control yaw and directional stability. Finally, twin engine designs may lend themselves more readily to the battle damage adaptable/re-configurable flight control systems that are just around the corner.

As in aerodynamic control surfaces, the further the control effector is located from the center of gravity of the aircraft; the greater control moment it can generate for the same force. In this manner the I_{ZZ} is a significant contributor to the control moment generated due to the thrust vector distance from the aircraft's center of gravity.

Lessons Learned

To be successful in a dynamic organization and flight test program requires many things. The most important ingredient being the people involved. We were fortunate to be working with the best group of individuals we have ever had the pleasure of working with.

From the highest ranks of management and leadership in the Navy, Marine Corps, the US Air Force, the German Air Force, NASA, ARPA, Rockwell International, and DASA right, down to the individual fueling the aircraft, we worked with the best.

In second place are three things often given lip service to, but which were actually

realized at the X-31 ITO. They are trust, cooperation and open minds. Not only were all the people involved given the opportunity to make their inputs, but they were all listened to and considered.

By virtue of this exchange of ideas, and innovative approaches we were able to brainstorm and maximize our talents.

The real success story here is not what was achieved with hardware or technology, but rather the people. Outstanding leadership and professionalism brought about this successful test program.

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